

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Bakirova Umida Bakhtiyor kizi

EXPERIMENTAL DEVELOPMENT WORK MONOLOGUE SPEECH OF OLDER CHILDREN

PRESCHOOL AGE IN THE PROCESS OF STORYTELLING

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/AVGUST

